

1st policy questionnaire: RELEVANT DOCUMENTS

Task 4.1 on the political economy of land use change focuses on understanding the institutional setting in each of the case studies. From an institutional perspective, policies are formal rules that frame and constrain the decision-making environment.

Here we would like you to indicate **which local, subnational or national policy documents (plans, strategies, etc.)** you consider **relevant or substantial** in the context of your **practice case**. The following questionnaire asks general questions such as thematic scope, scales and other characteristics of the document.

Please fill in the questionnaire for all relevant documents and **at least 6 documents**.

* Required

1. Indicate the PLUS Change practice case *

- Île-de-France Region (FR)
- Amsterdam (NL)
- Flanders (BE)
- Green Karst (SL)
- Kaigu peatland (LV)
- Lucca (IT)
- Mazovia Region (PL)
- Nitra City (SK)
- Parc Ela (CH)
- South Moravia (CZ)
- Surrey (UK)
- Three Countries Park (DE, BE, NL)
- Other

2. Title of the relevant document *

3. What is the scale of the policy document? (multiple choice possible) *

- Subnational (anything between national and local)
- National
- Local

4. How would you characterise the policy document according to the following categories? (multiple choice possible) *

- Strategy / Visionary (defines the long-term vision and pathways to reach this vision)
- Planning (defines framework, criteria for e.g. land use development in a mid-term)
- Regulation (legally binding commitments or decisions to steer implementation of plans and/or strategies)
- Programme / Action plan (a concrete plan/project implemented in short-term)
- Other

5. Indicate bindingness of the policy document *

- Binding
- Non-binding
- Combined

6. Which of the PLUS Change topics, if any, are addressed by this policy? (multiple choice possible) *

- Biodiversity
- Climate change
- Human wellbeing
- None of the above

7. Which thematic scope the policy document covers? (multiple choice possible) *

- Cultural heritage
- Land use management (e.g. landscape utilisation and management plan, etc.)
- Nature protection (e.g. protected site/area, preservation and enhancement of ecosystem functions and services, etc.)
- Natural resources management (e.g. soil, water, forest, etc.)
- Rural development
- Sectoral documents (e.g. agriculture, water management, forestry, economy, transport, energy, infrastructure, recreation, etc.)
- Urban development (e.g. master plan, zone plan, etc.)
- Other

8. Which land use systems the policy document addresses? (multiple choice possible) *

- Agriculture
- Energy infrastructure
- Forestry
- Industry and commerce
- Natural areas / green infrastructure
- Settlements
- Transport infrastructure
- Water / blue infrastructure
- Other

9. Please summarise the main (overall) objectives as stated by the policy document *

10. What is the importance of the policy document from the perspective of your practice case? *

- low (*the document is not that important for the case area/theme and/or its further development)
- medium (*the document is rather important for the case area/theme and/or its further development)
- high (*the document is very important for the case area/theme and/or its further development)

11. Provide a document source (web link if available)

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